

Marine Robotics Workshop

Friday 17th October 2025, **11.00-12.30 TBC**

hosted at the
Italian Conference on Robotics and Intelligent Machines
<https://i-rim.it/it/>
Rome, Gazometro Ostiense

Organizers

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Scope and format

Many of our country's vital interests, such as food and energy resources, strategic infrastructures, the protection of biodiversity, scientific research and technological development, are developed beneath the surface of the sea, where an important part of the history of our civilisation is also kept. The underwater world, whose abysses are still largely unexplored and unknown, represents the new scene of contention, on a geopolitical, economic and strategic level. In this context, marine robotics is a cutting-edge technology that is indispensable for present and future challenges.

The National Pole of the Underwater Dimension (PNS) was created as a response of the Country System to promote, facilitate and coordinate the cooperation of the different national excellences in the sector, in a synergic way. The Workshop aims to provide an up-to-date overview of current projects and future stages of the PNS roadmap.

Program

Start	End	Friday 17 th October 2025 @ I-RIM 3D	
11:00	11:10	Welcome, ISME	-
11:10	11:25	Speaker TBC	Italian Navy / PNS / CSSN
11:25	11:40	SIMILARS project (Speaker TBC)	FINCANTIERI SpA
11:40	11:55	OPTIMUS project (Speaker TBC)	FINCANTIERI SpA
11:55	12:10	MURENA project (Speaker TBC)	Leonardo SpA
12:10	12:25	TARAS project (Speaker TBC)	Wsense srl
12:25	12:30	Final discussion/greetings	-